

SYSTEM PROGRAMMING IN PHARMACEUTICAL MARKETING

Kh. O. Darmanov

e-mail: khakim.darmanov@mail.ru;

Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute; 5th year student of the Faculty of Pharmacy

Abstract: This thesis about System Programming in Pharmaceutical Marketing. The overall aim of this study is to examine firm strategic choices that trigger negative externalities culminating in market failure, system crisis, and public harm.

Key words: Pharmaceutical Marketing, Critical Marketing, Ethical Marketing, Stakeholders' Theory, Codes of Ethics

INTRODUCTION

A conceptual framework of marketing system crisis rooted in conflict of interests (COI) theory is used to make the following arguments: (1) marketing strategies emulated by the industry actors at micro level set lock in through path dependencies, (2) such path dependencies may be associated with negative externalities in the form of reduced quality of life of downstream stakeholders in adjacent systems, (3) back lash by system actors precipitates market failure inviting regulatory oversight in the form of fines that tarnish trust and firm reputation, (4) with implications for system crisis and public welfare. Communication is indispensable for an organisation's viability and value creation (Prins & Verhoef, 2007). The discipline of marketing is responsible for communicating and delivering value to customers by keeping in view the larger interests of society. However, in real-world practice, marketing breaches ethical lines in the exchange process and might favour profits over society's long term benefits (Jones et al., 2007). Marketing and society are interconnected and significantly influence each other. Marketing is inextricably connected with economic growth (Kinsey, 1982), but at the same time is a bad name as well. Deception and exploitation are other names for marketing because the discipline is responsible for promoting materialism and over consumption overhauled if the key stakeholders, particularly industry and physicians behave ethically and comply with codes of conduct developed by international and local bodies. The principles, strategies and tactics, and outcomes of marketing are under scrutiny and criticism. Nevertheless, constructive criticism helps to affirmatively connect both society and discipline.

The overriding focus of marketing on instrumentalism rather than critical reflexivity (Clifford, 2007); overemphasis on narrow managerial priorities and consumer self-interest; complacency in handling environmental issues; intellectual shallowness by not developing theory; and stress on quantitative modelling are the imperfections which need to be critiqued (Alvesson, 1994; Tadajewski, 2006). Nonetheless, criticism on these avenues will not only improve the intellectual capacity but will boost credibility in the marketplace. The critical perspective of marketing becomes much more important in some industries like food, pharmaceuticals, and tobacco. It is more likely that critical marketing discipline will be employed in situations like tobacco and pharmaceutical drug promotion. It is marketing that is responsible for the smoking of adults in society. It is for this very reason that WHO and other international organisations have completely banned the promotion of tobacco products in all member countries. The overuse and even abuse of antibiotics is also attributed to marketing. The human race is very close to the pre-antibiotic era by misuse of this wonderful drug and

failure to innovate. Nevertheless, pharmaceutical marketing is equally blameworthy of over-promotion and inability to allocate proper R&D budgets for new molecule development. The influence of pharmaceutical marketing on physicians' prescribing pattern is studied qualitatively, and thus, need to inquire through survey research to make the intervention easy wherever required. This study doesn't develop a proper tool to gauge physicians' prescriptions which may be research in future studies.

Likewise, the Pakistani chapter also acts as a catalyst for boosting the economy and creates millions of jobs. Nevertheless, unethical marketing practices are the norms of the industry operating in Pakistan. They are competing with each other in bribing physicians, providing lavish dinners, expensive gifts, and overseas entertainment tours instead of academic trips. Marketers employ manipulative strategies to induce consumers which result in the overconsumption and misuse of non-renewable resources. They expand current markets by producing large volume sales and profits and thus, increase shareholders' wealth. The current advent of antibiotic resistance is attributed to the misuse and abuse of this wonderful drug and pharmaceutical marketing has a prominent role in it. Marketing as a discipline creates value by informing physicians to prescribe the right drugs in appropriate indication with proper dosage. But nonetheless, the industry used marketing as an instrumentalist tool to expand the boundaries of current treatments and thus, increase the usage of medicines unnecessarily. However, unethical marketing practices have firmly anchored their roots in the pharmaceutical industry. There is a growing concern over health-related issues that arise from the influence of unethical marketing on drug dispensing.

CONCLUSION

Safe and potent drug discovery, manufacturing, and marketing are the overarching goals for the pharmaceutical industry with the aim of improving quality of life and increasing average life span. In this way, they safeguard the shareholders' wealth and create value in the form of new molecule development. Thus, the larger interests of the society and community are preserved. The pharmaceutical industry is a multi-billion-dollar industry contributing \$1.3 trillion to the world global economy and has provided millions of jobs to society.

REFERENCES

1. Abela, Andrew V., & Murphy, Patrick E. (2008).
2. Marketing with integrity: ethics and the service-dominant logic for marketing.
3. Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science, 36(1), 39-53. doi: 10.1007/s11747-007-0062-0 Agee, Jane. (2009).
4. Developing qualitative research questions: a reflective process. International Journal of Qualitative Studies in Education, 22(4), 431-447. doi: 10.1080/09518390902736512 Alvesson, Mats. (1994).
5. Critical theory and consumer marketing. Scandinavian journal of management, 10(3), 291-313. Bartels, Robert. (1967).
6. A model for ethics in marketing. The Journal of Marketing, 20-26. Birks, Melanie, Chapman, Ysanne, & Francis, Karen. (2008).
7. Memoing in qualitative research: Probing data and processes. Journal of Research in Nursing, 13(1), 68-75. doi: 10.1177/1744987107081254 Burton, Dawn. (2001).